

Critical Exponents of Dynamic Percolation Universality Class: the Renormalization Group Approach

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In this study we focus on the non-equilibrium phase transition whose asymptotic critical behavior is governed by the dynamic isotropic percolation universality class. In order to quantitatively characterize universal properties associated with this class, we employ a field-theoretic formulation of the model augmented with perturbative renormalization group technique. Utilizing such approach enables us to systematically compute the critical exponents in higher orders of perturbation theory. In particular, we perform an analysis to the three-loop precision. To this order we determine the renormalization constants and present relations for critical exponents in terms of critical dimensions. Finally, we also present numerically estimated values of critical exponents obtained from perturbation theory.

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1. Introduction

Non-equilibrium dynamic phase transitions between absorbing and active states is a well established topic in the study of dynamic phenomena [1]. Similar to the critical statics, critical-like behavior with pronounced large-scale correlations is expected. Such behavior can be associated with a certain universality class[2]. Each class is characterized by a set of critical exponents that fully describe scaling behavior of physically interesting

quantities such as correlation or response functions. These exponents are universal in the sense that they can depend only on the gross properties of the system under study, such as the number of components of an order parameter or spatial dimension, and do not depend on specific microscopic details such as a type of underlying lattice structure or precise values of phenomenological constants. The typical quantitative goal of the theory is to determine values of these critical exponents. In contrast to the static phase transitions, dynamic phase transitions often exhibit richer behavior. In broad terms, they can be classified [2] into two distinct families: first, systems that possess a static limit (for instance, systems that are in thermal equilibrium and whose steady state is described by appropriate Boltzmann weight) and second, systems that are genuine non-equilibrium (a typical example is fully developed turbulence for which one can not reasonably define a steady state). The first family

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includes models like the famous φ^4 model or dynamic isotropic percolation (DyIP), whose quasi-static limit corresponds to the standard percolation models [3]. The prototypical example of the second family is a process known as directed percolation (DP), which lacks a static counterpart. For dynamic transitions, the universality class is typically described by four independent exponents, with the remaining exponents derivable through various scaling relations. However, additional symmetries in the model may lead to a reduction of the actual number of independent exponents.

In what follows, an important role is played by the upper critical dimension d_c . Similarly to static phase transitions, above d_c , mean-field approximation (which effectively amounts to a neglect of order parameter fluctuations) provides exact values of critical exponents [2]. These often take the form of simple rational numbers. On the other hand, below d_c , mean-field theory necessarily breaks down since it does not account for now relevant fluctuations of an order parameter. At the critical dimension d_c , renormalization group (RG) theory predicts mean-field behavior with logarithmic corrections [2].

Traditionally, the aforementioned families can also be distinguished from another point of view. Interpreting spreading dynamics as a particular epidemic process, dynamic percolation models can be divided into two prominent categories:

1. Directed percolation, characterized by a preferred spreading direction (often interpreted as time direction in epidemics interpretation), with an upper critical dimension $d_c = 4$.
2. Isotropic percolation, in which spreading occurs uniformly in all spatial directions. The upper critical dimension for DyIP is $d_c = 6$.

To compute critical exponents below the critical dimension d_c , quantum field theory methods and RG techniques are of particular importance. They not only provide a sophisticated and

powerful framework but also offer various methods suitable for practical calculations. For our purposes, the most relevant are the field-theoretic approach, the Feynman diagrammatic technique, and ultraviolet (UV) renormalization [1, 2]. In the end, proper application of these methods typically results in asymptotic series expansions for the critical exponents, which can be further refined by additional resummation methods to enhance convergence properties of the calculated series. To date, universal static properties of isotropic percolation processes have been analyzed up to the five-loop precision in the perturbation theory [4]. For DP process, the asymptotic series for critical exponents have been extended to the three-loop approximation [5]. For DyIP, the similar level of precision with respect to the dynamics was obtained only recently [6]. As previously noted, DyIP process possesses a quasi-static limit, which allowed us in this work to concentrate solely on its dynamic aspects in our calculations.

In the following section, we will examine the functional integral formulations (i.e., through continuous stochastic fields whose configurations are weighted by a certain action functional) of both static and dynamic properties DyIP process and briefly derive the relations necessary for the full three-loop computation of RG constants. Finally, we will present current estimates for the critical exponents of the DyIP universality class, obtained via quantum field theory and subsequent RG analysis [4, 6].

2. Percolation

Let us start with the static part of the DyIP process, which corresponds to the standard percolation model. A fundamental example is a percolation process on a two-dimensional square lattice, which occurs in two variants: *bond percolation*, in which bonds between sites are open with a probability p while all sites are occupied (see Fig. 1), and *site percolation*, where sites are occupied with probability p with all bonds connected. It is well-known that these two systems exhibit two distinct

FIG. 1: Two possible realizations of the bond percolation on the (13×13) square lattice corresponding to inactive phase (left) and active phase (right), respectively. Note the existence of a percolating cluster in the latter that connects any two sides of the lattice.

phases: an absorbing phase ($p < p_c$) and an active phase ($p > p_c$), separated by a continuous phase transition at the critical threshold p_c . The exact critical values are $p_c = \frac{1}{2}$ for bond percolation and $p_c = 0.59274605079210(2)$ for site percolation [7]. Notably, both systems exhibit identical critical behavior near p_c , characterized by the same set of critical exponents that thus defines the standard percolation universality class. These exponents are universal quantities, i.e., being independent of both the lattice geometry (square, triangular, ...) and the specific percolation type (bond or site).

In general, critical exponents for the universality class can not be determined exactly, and one has to resolve to some approximation scheme [3, 8]. Here, we present such a scheme utilizing methods of quantum field theory and RG technique (commonly called the field-theoretic approach in the literature). For the static case, critical exponents (see Tab. 1) have been computed up to the fifth order in perturbation theory [4]. The field-theoretic analysis begins with the action functional of the percolation model, and below we present all currently known formulations of the corresponding actions for percolation processes. Action functionals we will later provide,

in principle, fully encode all necessary information about the critical exponents of the standard percolation universality class.

The standard quantum field formulation for static properties of isotropic percolation model is related to the action functional the φ^3 model with a general cubic interaction term [4]

$$\mathcal{S}(\hat{\varphi}) = -\int d^d x \left[\frac{1}{2} (\nabla \hat{\varphi}_i)^2 + \frac{1}{2} \hat{\tau} \hat{\varphi}_i^2 + \frac{\hat{g}}{3!} d_{ijkl} \hat{\varphi}_i \hat{\varphi}_j \hat{\varphi}_k \hat{\varphi}_l \right], \tag{1}$$

where d is the space dimension, $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, \dots, x_d)$ is d -dimensional spatial vector, $\hat{\varphi} = \hat{\varphi}(\mathbf{x})$ is an unrenormalized (bare) field of the model, $\nabla = (\partial/\partial x_1, \dots, \partial/\partial x_d)$ is a spatial gradient, $\hat{\tau}$ is a mass-like parameter proportional to a deviation from the critical percolation probability, and \hat{g} is a charge of the model. The weight $\exp\{\mathcal{S}(\hat{\varphi})\}$ is analogous to the Boltzmann weight in classical thermodynamics, since it measure a relative probability of a given field configuration [2]. Hereinafter, the symbol "o" always denotes bare fields and parameters in the RG procedure. For the percolation model, the tensor d_{ijkl} takes the form of the n -dimensional tetrahedron. This is relevant for a description of the critical behavior of

Table 1: Values of critical exponents of the percolation universality class for different space dimensions. The dimension $d = 6$ (equal to the upper critical dimension d_c of the model) yields corresponding mean-field values; values for space dimensions $d \in \{3, 4, 5\}$ are taken from Ref. [4], and for $d = 2$ from Ref. [8], respectively.

d	α	β	γ	δ	$\nu \equiv \nu_{\perp}$	η	σ	τ
6	-1	1	1	2	0.5	0	0.5	2.5
5	-0.870(1)	0.8452(2)	1.1792(7)	2.3952(12)	0.5739(1)	-0.0547(10)	0.49396(13)	2.4175(2)
4	-0.75(2)	0.658(1)	1.430(6)	3.175(8)	0.686(2)	-0.084(4)	0.4789(14)	2.3150(8)
3	-0.64(4)	0.429(4)	1.78(3)	5.16(4)	0.88(2)	-0.03(1)	0.452(7)	2.1938(12)
2	$-\frac{2}{3}$	$\frac{5}{36}$	$\frac{43}{18}$	$\frac{91}{5}$	$\frac{4}{3}$	$\frac{5}{24}$	$\frac{36}{91}$	$\frac{197}{91}$

$(n+1)$ -state Potts model [4, 9], in which the corresponding tensor can be expressed in the following way

$$d_{ijkl} = \sum_{\alpha=1}^{n+1} e_{\alpha}^i e_{\alpha}^j e_{\alpha}^k e_{\alpha}^l, \quad (2)$$

where e_1^i, \dots, e_{n+1}^i are n dimensional vectors. The standard percolation process can be understood as a specific limit of the general model (1), in which the vectors of tetrahedron obey additional algebraic relations

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\alpha=1}^{n+1} e_{\alpha}^i &= 0, & \sum_{\alpha=1}^{n+1} e_{\alpha}^i e_{\alpha}^j &= (n+1)\delta_{ij}, \\ \sum_{i=1}^n e_{\alpha}^i e_{\beta}^i &= (n+1)\delta_{\alpha\beta} - 1, \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where δ_{ij} ($\delta_{\alpha\beta}$) is the Kronecker delta. The actual calculations are carried out for the general value of the parameter n , and in the end we contract indices between interaction vertices taking into account the rules (3). Finally, we take the limit $n \rightarrow 0$ to arrive at the genuine percolation problem [9].

The second formulation is built by an inclusion of a new "ghost"-like (term borrowed from non-abelian gauge theories) field $\dot{\psi}$ [10]. In this formulation, the action functional with one com-

ponent fields $(\dot{\varphi}, \dot{\psi})$ takes the form

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{S}(\dot{\varphi}, \dot{\psi}) &= - \int d^d x \left[\frac{1}{2} (\nabla \dot{\varphi})^2 - \frac{1}{2} (\nabla \dot{\psi})^2 \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{1}{2} \tau (\dot{\varphi}^2 - \dot{\psi}^2) + \frac{g}{3!} (\dot{\varphi} + \dot{\psi})^3 \right], \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

augmented with an additional rule that only Feynman diagrams with external tails connected via $\langle \dot{\varphi} \dot{\varphi} \rangle$ propagator are included. If this propagator is not present in a Feynman diagram, this diagram does not contribute. In fact, this property is a consequence of the first algebraic identity in (3). It was proven [11] that in perturbation expansion for two-point Green's function, the overall sign in an one-particle irreducible diagram depends on a number of loops in the given diagram. More details about this field-theoretic approach and its derivations can be found in the literature [10].

The third formulation is given by the quasi-static limit of the field-theoretic formulation of DyIP [3]. The structure of quasi-static limits leads to the action

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{S}(\dot{\psi}', \dot{\varphi}) &= - \int d^d x \left[(\nabla \dot{\psi}') \cdot (\nabla \dot{\varphi}) + \dot{\tau} \dot{\psi}' \dot{\varphi} \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{\dot{\lambda}}{2!} \dot{\psi}' (\dot{\varphi} - \dot{\psi}') \dot{\varphi} \right], \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where the field notation is chosen in such a way that allows a direct passage to the dynamic generalization. Within this formulation, it is further necessary to add a supplemental condition according to which Feynman diagrams with closed loops

of propagators $\langle \dot{\psi}' \dot{\varphi} \rangle$ must be discarded. As can be easily seen in this formulation, for a Feynman diagram contributing to the two-point Green's function, the overall sign depends on the number of loops in the diagram. By direct inspection of diagrams, we can infer that the total number of loops n_{loop} in a diagram can be expressed via its number of interaction vertices $(n_{\psi' \psi' \varphi} + n_{\psi' \varphi \varphi})$. Because the number of vertices $n_{\psi' \psi' \varphi}$ is the same as $n_{\psi' \varphi \varphi}$ in two-point diagrams, with the vertices differing only by a numerical factor -1 (see action functional (5)), it follows that, as in the previous model, the overall sign in diagram depends on a number of loops $n_{loop} = n_{\psi' \psi' \varphi} = n_{\psi' \varphi \varphi}$. To the best of our knowledge there does not yet exist direct (combinatorial) proof of the relationship between the action functional of the quasi-static limit (5) and the functional (1) or (4), respectively.

For brevity, we skip details about the model (5). Let us just mention that it can be shown that the model is multiplicatively renormalizable and its renormalized action takes the form

$$\mathcal{S}_R(\psi', \varphi) = - \int d^d x \left[Z_2 (\nabla \psi') \cdot (\nabla \varphi) + Z_3 \tau \psi' \varphi + Z_4 \frac{\lambda \mu^{\varepsilon/2}}{2!} \psi' (\varphi - \psi') \varphi \right], \quad (6)$$

where μ is a renormalization mass and ε will be defined later. The notation for RG constants is chosen in a way to provide direct matching with a dynamic case. In critical statics, the calculation of RG constants leads to the same values as for the DyIP. Let us stress that evaluating RG constants in statics is a much less demanding task than evaluating Feynman diagrams in dynamic models.

3. Dynamic Isotropic Percolation

In a lattice formulation, DyIP is modeled through random processes in which agents (objects) spread uniformly in all directions subject to certain reaction schemes [1]. The process is

usually initialized by putting an initial seed localized at the origin. For DyIP on a square lattice, the critical probability p_c coincides with that of the standard percolation process. As in the static case, the system exhibits two distinct phases with respect to the large scale behavior: an absorbing phase and an active phase. In Fig. 2 we qualitatively illustrate these two phases, with the origin marked by a black square in both configurations.

A key feature of DyIP is its reproduction of static percolation critical exponents in the quasi-static limit ($t \rightarrow \infty$). This correspondence mirrors the relationship between the φ^4 model and model A of critical dynamics [12], where static and dynamic critical behaviors coincide under appropriate limits. Like static percolation, DyIP shares the same upper critical dimension $d_c = 6$. Above this dimension, mean-field theory provides exact values for the dynamic critical exponents. However, for $d = 2$, no exact analytical solution is known for dynamic exponents.

To apply field-theoretic methods, the percolation stochastic problem is reformulated using a functional approach. Following established procedures, we rewrite the DyIP process into an action functional [3, 6], which serves as the basis for our perturbative analysis. The specific form of this functional is given by:

$$\mathcal{S} = - \int d^d x \int dt \left[\dot{\psi}' \left(\partial_t - \dot{D} \nabla^2 + \dot{D} \hat{\tau} \right) \dot{\psi} + \frac{\dot{D} \dot{\lambda}}{2} \left(2 \dot{\psi}' \dot{\psi} \dot{\varphi} - \dot{\psi}'^2 \dot{\psi} \right) \right], \quad (7)$$

where \dot{D} is a bare diffusion constant, ∇^2 is the Laplace operator and the following relation between fields is satisfied

$$\partial_t \dot{\varphi}(t, \mathbf{x}) = \dot{D} \dot{\psi}(t, \mathbf{x}), \quad \text{or} \\ \dot{\varphi}(t, \mathbf{x}) = \dot{D} \int_{-\infty}^t dt' \dot{\psi}(t', \mathbf{x}). \quad (8)$$

The presence of the diffusion constant in the interaction terms in the action (7) is purely for technical dimensional reasons. In the stochastic formulation, the field $\dot{\varphi}$ as the density of generated

FIG. 2: Two realizations of different phases of the bond DyIP on the square lattice with the size 13. The starting point is in the center denoted by a black square.

debris [3] is expressed through the field ψ . In fact, this field plays a crucial role in establishing the static limit of the theory [3]. The analysis proceeds by considering a process initially localized at time instant $t = 0$, while focusing on the large-time asymptotic behavior (i.e., the limit $t = \infty$) of Green's functions of the debris field. The quasi-static limit is obtained through the transformations $\psi'(t, \mathbf{x}) = \psi'(0, \mathbf{x}) \equiv \psi'(\mathbf{x})$ and final density of debris $\dot{\varphi}(\mathbf{x}) = \dot{D} \int_0^\infty dt \psi(t, \mathbf{x})$. These transformations naturally lead to the quasi-static model introduced in Eq. (5).

The DyIP model possesses a fundamental dual symmetry that can be compactly expressed by the field transformation $\psi'(t, \mathbf{x}) \leftrightarrow -\dot{\varphi}(-t, \mathbf{x})$. In other words, we can say that this symmetry represents an exact mapping between the response field ψ' and the debris density field $\dot{\varphi}$ under the time inversion. Although it is strictly valid only asymptotically, its presence has an important practical consequence. Namely, that only three independent critical exponents are needed to fully characterize the universality class of DyIP [3].

The field-theoretic formulation provides a systematic approach for computing correlation

and response functions through the generating functional:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{W}(A) &= \ln \int \mathcal{D}\Psi \exp \{ \mathcal{S} + A\Psi \}, \\ A\Psi &= \int dx \left[A^\psi \psi + A^{\psi'} \psi' \right], \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where $\mathcal{D}\Psi = \mathcal{D}\psi' \mathcal{D}\psi$ denotes the functional integration measure, $A = (A^\psi, A^{\psi'})$ are source fields, and $dx = d^d x dt$. The central objects of our analysis are the irreducible Green's functions Γ (definition and relevant properties can be found in the literature [1, 2]), obtained as Legendre transforms of $\mathcal{W}[A]$. In quantum field theory, the perturbative approach begins by expressing such irreducible Green's functions as a series of Feynman diagrams, where the formal importance of each diagram is governed by the interaction parameters (coupling constants) it contains. This systematic expansion enables the calculation of critical exponents through RG analysis, where the asymptotic behavior is extracted from the scaling properties of these Green's functions.

The RG analysis begins with dimensional considerations (i.e., the standard analysis of canonical dimensions) of the model parameters.

It is straightforward to show [3] that the theory becomes logarithmic at the critical dimension $d_c = 6$, where the coupling constant λ becomes dimensionless. In order to regularize Feynman diagrams we employ dimensional regularization, which consists in considering space dimension as an additional (complex) variable [2]. The formal expansion parameter of the theory then becomes a deviation from the upper critical dimension:

$$\varepsilon \equiv d_c - d = 6 - d. \quad (10)$$

For the logarithmic theory, the total canonical dimension $d[\Gamma^{(n_{\psi'}, n_{\psi})}]$ represents the formal degree of UV divergence, which manifest themselves and in a Green's functions as various poles in the parameter ε . The crucial step in the RG procedure lies in systematic removal of superficial UV divergences.

Considering the above action (7) and taking into account dual symmetry, the renormalized action functional takes the following compact (needed integrals are implicitly implied) form:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{S}_R = & \psi' (-Z_1 \partial_t + Z_2 D \nabla^2 - Z_3 D \tau) \psi \\ & + \frac{D \lambda \mu^{\varepsilon/2}}{2} Z_4 (\psi'^2 \psi - 2 \psi' \psi \varphi), \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

where $Z_i (i = 1, 2, 3, 4)$ are RG constants that can be determined perturbatively.

A complete treatment of the three-loop Feynman diagrams calculation is available in our previous work [6]. In the present work, we focus specifically on determining the coefficients of the RG constants within the minimal subtraction (MS) scheme. In the MS scheme, renormalization constants do not depend on dimensional parameters μ, τ in perturbation theory and have general form

$$Z_i \equiv Z_i(g, \varepsilon) = 1 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} g^n \sum_{s=1}^n \frac{z_{n,s}^{(i)}}{\varepsilon^s}. \quad (12)$$

For DyIP process, the coefficients of RG constants up to the second order have the following values

$$\begin{aligned} Z_1 : \quad & z_{1,1}^{(1)} = \frac{3}{4}, & z_{2,2}^{(1)} = \frac{51}{32}, & z_{2,1}^{(1)} = \frac{1}{64} \left(-\frac{227}{6} + 10 \ln 2 - 9 \ln 3 \right); \\ Z_2 : \quad & z_{1,1}^{(2)} = \frac{1}{6}, & z_{2,2}^{(2)} = \frac{11}{36}, & z_{2,1}^{(2)} = -\frac{37}{432}; \\ Z_3 : \quad & z_{1,1}^{(3)} = 1, & z_{2,2}^{(3)} = \frac{9}{4}, & z_{2,1}^{(3)} = -\frac{47}{48}; \\ Z_4 : \quad & z_{1,1}^{(4)} = 2, & z_{2,2}^{(4)} = \frac{11}{2}, & z_{2,1}^{(4)} = -\frac{59}{24}. \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

To systematically compute the RG constants at the next order, several key quantities have to be introduced first. To derive the coefficients of the RG constants, the contributions from Feynman diagrams (corresponding to one-particle ir-

reducible Green's functions) have to be properly normalized. The normalized contribution to the Green's functions $\Gamma_i; i = 1, 2, 3, 4$ are then determined from these diagrams as follows:

$$\Gamma_1 \equiv \frac{\partial \Gamma^{(1,1)}}{\partial i\omega} \Big|_{\mathbf{p}=0, \omega=0}, \Gamma_2 \equiv -\frac{1}{2\mathring{D}} \frac{\partial^2 \Gamma^{(1,1)}}{\partial \mathbf{p}^2} \Big|_{\mathbf{p}=0, \omega=0}, \Gamma_3 \equiv -\frac{1}{\mathring{D}} \frac{\partial \Gamma^{(1,1)}}{\partial \tau^2} \Big|_{\mathbf{p}=0, \omega=0}, \Gamma_4 \equiv \frac{1}{\mathring{D}\lambda} \Gamma^{(1,2)} \Big|_{\mathbf{p}=0, \omega=0}, \quad (14)$$

where \mathbf{p} , ω are external momentum and frequency of Feynman diagrams entering perturbative expansion of a given Γ_i function, respectively. These quantities Γ_i , $i = 1, 2, 3, 4$ are dimensionless and their normalization $\Gamma_i = 1$ for $\lambda = 0$. Details about the calculation for Γ_1 can be found in Ref. [6] and about calculation of the other Γ_i in the Ref. [13]. Let us focus our attention on the determination of coefficients of RG constants. In the formulation (14), the renormalized Green function has form

$$\Gamma_{iR} = Z_i \left[1 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} Z_g^n Z_\tau^{-n\epsilon/2} (-g)^n \left(\frac{\mu^2}{\tau} \right)^{n\epsilon/2} \Gamma_i^{(n)} \right], \quad (15)$$

where the $\Gamma_i^{(n)} \equiv \Gamma_i^{(n)}(\epsilon)$ are the sum of the n -loop contribution from the Feynman diagrams. In perturbative calculation, it is more convenient to introduce a new coupling constant g , defined as follows:

$$g \equiv \lambda^2 \frac{\Gamma(1 + \epsilon/2)}{(4\pi)^{3-\epsilon/2}}. \quad (16)$$

Formally, the rescaling $\lambda^2 \rightarrow g$ leads to the use of the modified minimal subtraction $\overline{\text{MS}}$ scheme instead of the previously mentioned MS scheme [2].

In the $\overline{\text{MS}}$ scheme, the RG constants are determined by setting $\tau = \mu^2$. This choice ensures that the coefficients of $\ln(\mu^2/\tau)$ in the expansion vanish when combined with the poles in ϵ . However, if these terms are retained and the expansion is carried out, the higher-order coefficients can be expressed recursively in terms of the lower-order RG constants. Specifically, these are the coefficients not associated with poles ϵ^{-1} . The procedure begins by incorporating all relevant terms at the desired order in perturbation theory and up

to the three-loop as follows:

$$0 = Z_i + g m^{\epsilon/2} Z Z_i \Gamma_i^{(1)} + g^2 m^\epsilon Z^2 Z_i \Gamma_i^{(2)} + g^3 m^{3\epsilon/2} Z^3 Z_i \Gamma_i^{(3)} + O(g^4), \quad (17)$$

where we have introduced abbreviations $m \equiv (\mu^2/\tau)$ and $Z \equiv Z_g Z_\tau^{-\epsilon/2}$. The left-hand side of Eq. (17) does not contain poles in ϵ , requiring all divergent terms to cancel on the right-hand side up to UV-finite contributions. More precisely, the equality is established order-by-order in perturbation theory by matching the coefficients at identical powers of the coupling constant g and the pole terms involving the logarithm $\ln m$. For example, at the two-loop level we get a pole term of the following form:

$$0 = \frac{g^2}{\epsilon} \ln m \left[-\frac{1}{2} a_{11}^{(i)} z_{1,1}^{(i)} + \Gamma_i^{(2,2)} \right] \rightarrow z_{2,2}^{(i)} = \frac{1}{2} z_{1,1}^{(i)} a_{1,1}^{(i)}, \quad (18)$$

where $\Gamma_i^{(2,2)}$ denotes a numerical coefficient associated with the second order poles ϵ^{-2} in two-loop calculation $\Gamma_i^{(2)}$. Through direct algebraic manipulation, the contribution $\Gamma_i^{(2,2)}$ can be expressed as a combination of lower-order RG constant coefficients, which are then incorporated into the relation for the coefficient $z_{2,2}^{(i)}$. Similarly, we can derive the corresponding relations for the g^3 coefficients as follows:

$$z_{3,3}^{(i)} = -\frac{1}{3} \left[-2a_{2,2}^{(i)} z_{1,1}^{(i)} + \left(2a_{1,1}^{(i)} - z_{1,1}^{(i)} \right) z_{2,2}^{(i)} \right], \quad (19)$$

$$z_{3,2}^{(i)} = -\frac{1}{3} \left[-2z_{1,1}^{(i)} a_{2,1}^{(i)} - 2a_{1,1}^{(i)} z_{2,1}^{(i)} + z_{1,1}^{(i)} z_{2,1}^{(i)} + a_{1,0} z_{1,1}^{(i)} \left(3a_{1,1}^{(i)} - z_{1,1}^{(i)} \right) \right], \quad (20)$$

where the coefficients $a^{(i)}$ enter the following perturbative expansion

$$Z_i Z = 1 + g \left(\frac{a_{1,1}^{(i)}}{\varepsilon} + a_{1,0} \right) + g^2 \left(\frac{a_{2,2}^{(i)}}{\varepsilon^2} + \frac{a_{2,1}^{(i)}}{\varepsilon} + a_{2,0} \right) + O(g^3). \quad (21)$$

In the expansion, the coefficients have following form:

$$\begin{aligned} a_{1,1}^{(i)} &= -3z_{1,1}^{(2)} + 2z_{1,1}^{(4)} + z_{1,1}^{(i)}, & a_{1,0} &= \frac{1}{2} (z_{1,1}^{(2)} - z_{1,1}^{(3)}), \\ a_{2,2}^{(i)} &= 6 \left(z_{1,1}^{(2)} \right)^2 - 3z_{2,2}^{(2)} + \left(z_{1,1}^{(4)} \right)^2 + 2z_{2,2}^{(4)} + 2z_{1,1}^{(4)} z_{1,1}^{(i)} - 3z_{1,1}^{(2)} z_{1,1}^{(i)} - 6z_{1,1}^{(2)} z_{1,1}^{(4)} + z_{2,2}^{(i)}, \\ a_{2,1}^{(i)} &= \frac{1}{4} \left[\left(z_{1,1}^{(3)} \right)^2 - 7 \left(z_{1,1}^{(2)} \right)^2 - 12z_{2,1}^{(2)} + 2z_{2,2}^{(2)} - 2z_{2,2}^{(3)} - 4z_{1,1}^{(3)} z_{1,1}^{(4)} + 8z_{2,1}^{(4)} \right. \\ &\quad \left. - 2z_{1,1}^{(3)} z_{1,1}^{(i)} + 2z_{1,1}^{(2)} \left(3z_{1,1}^{(3)} + 2z_{1,1}^{(4)} + z_{1,1}^{(i)} \right) + 4z_{2,1}^{(i)} \right]. \end{aligned}$$

The final values for coefficients of RG constants

from relations (18), (19) and (20) are

$$\begin{aligned} Z_1 : \quad z_{2,2}^{(1)} &= \frac{51}{32}, & z_{3,3}^{(1)} &= -\frac{527}{128}, & z_{3,2}^{(1)} &= \frac{-1}{128} \left(\frac{19135}{36} - \frac{185}{3} \ln 2 + \frac{111}{2} \ln 3 \right); \\ Z_2 : \quad z_{2,2}^{(2)} &= \frac{11}{36}, & z_{3,3}^{(2)} &= \frac{473}{648}, & z_{3,2}^{(2)} &= -\frac{1897}{2592}; \\ Z_3 : \quad z_{2,2}^{(3)} &= \frac{9}{4}, & z_{3,3}^{(3)} &= 6, & z_{3,2}^{(3)} &= -\frac{172}{27}; \\ Z_4 : \quad z_{2,2}^{(4)} &= \frac{11}{2}, & z_{3,3}^{(4)} &= \frac{33}{2}, & z_{3,2}^{(4)} &= -\frac{3643}{216}. \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

The results agree with the established values for the RG constant coefficients (i = 2, 3, 4) reported in the past [13]. For the RG constant Z_1 , the analytic agreement for coefficients $z_{3,3}^{(1)}$ and $z_{2,2}^{(1)}$ with established expressions [6] and the numerical consistency for $z_{3,2}^{(1)}$ within computational accuracy [6]:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{relation: } z_{3,2}^{(1)} &\approx -4.294974, \\ \text{numeric: } z_{3,2}^{(1)} &= -4.29497(3). \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

Having determined the renormalization constants, we can now examine the model's asymptotic behavior and calculate the corresponding critical exponents. The complete computation of these exponents can be found elsewhere [6], our present focus is on the definition of anomalous dimensions and their connection to RG constants:

$$\gamma_i \equiv \mu \partial_\mu \left|_{\circ} \ln Z_i \right. \longrightarrow \gamma_i = - \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} g^n n z_{n,1}^{(i)}, \quad (24)$$

where $\partial_\mu|_0$ stands for the partial derivative taken at the fixed bare parameters. The second representation of the anomalous dimension, derived specifically for the $\overline{\text{MS}}$ scheme [2], follows from the standard RG analysis.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Static: } \Delta_{\psi'} &= \frac{d-2+\gamma_2^*}{2}, & \Delta_\tau &= 2+\gamma_3^*-\gamma_2^*, & \Delta_{\psi'} &= \Delta_\varphi, \\ \text{Dynamic: } \Delta_\psi &= \frac{d+2-\gamma_2^*}{2}+\gamma_1^*, & \Delta_\omega &= 2+\gamma_2^*-\gamma_1^*, & \Delta_\psi - \Delta_{\psi'} &= \Delta_\omega, \end{aligned} \tag{25}$$

where $\gamma_i^* \equiv \gamma_i(g^*)$ represents an anomalous dimension γ_i evaluated at the fixed point. The coordinate g^* of the non-trivial fixed point is de-

termined from the beta function $\beta(g) = -g(\varepsilon + 2\gamma_4 - 3\gamma_2)$ by the condition $\beta(g^*) = 0$. In the static limit, the critical exponents take the form:

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha &= 2 - \frac{d}{\Delta_\tau}, & \beta &= \frac{\Delta_{\psi'}}{\Delta_\tau}, & \gamma &= \frac{d-2\Delta_{\psi'}}{\Delta_\tau}, & \delta &= \frac{d}{\Delta_{\psi'}} - 1, \\ \nu_\perp &= \frac{1}{\Delta_\tau}, & \eta &= 2 - d + 2\Delta_{\psi'}, & \sigma &= \frac{\Delta_\tau}{d - \Delta_{\psi'}}, & \tau &= 1 + \frac{d}{d - \Delta_{\psi'}}, \end{aligned} \tag{26}$$

with values summarized in Tab. 1. However, a complete description of the DyIP universality class requires inclusion of the dynamic part. For the dynamic case, we choose one critical dimension and express the remaining critical exponents using the Δ_ω as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} z &= \Delta_\omega, & z_s &= \frac{2}{\Delta_\omega}, & \theta_s &= \frac{d-2\Delta_{\psi'}}{\Delta_\omega} - 1, \\ \delta_s &= \frac{\Delta_{\psi'}}{\Delta_\omega}, & \nu_\parallel &= \frac{\Delta_\omega}{\Delta_\tau}. \end{aligned} \tag{27}$$

The three-loop calculation results for these critical exponents are presented in Tab. 2. These values show good agreement with lattice simulations [14] in space dimensions five and four, respectively. However, for the physically most interesting cases of space dimensions three and two, the current resummation techniques do not provide

quantitatively satisfactory estimates. The question of whether higher-order calculations might improve this precision remains open for the future investigation.

Table 2: Dynamic critical exponents of DyIP universality class. The results for $d = 6$ correspond to the mean-field prediction, and for $d < 6$ they are taken from the work [6].

d	z_s	z	θ_s	δ_s	ν_\parallel
6	1	2	0	1	1
5	1.099(7)	1.820(12)	1.130(3)	0.809(2)	1.045(5)
4	1.22(5)	1.64(7)	0.28(2)	0.578(11)	1.13(4)
3	1.35(17)	1.48(19)	0.39(7)	0.32(2)	1.32(12)
2	1.5(4)	1.3(4)	0.2(2)	0.14(9)	1.5(3)

4. Conclusion

In this contribution, we have given a brief overview of the main findings of our analysis of critical exponents describing the DyIP universality class. Renormalization analysis is performed up to the third order in perturbation theory with demonstrated justification through consistent cancelation of all UV divergences. All dimensional terms in final expressions drop out, more precisely, the performed three-loop consistency checks show that all logarithmic divergences $\ln(\mu^2/\tau)$ systematically cancel out in the final expressions. It turns out that the interaction term $\psi'\psi\varphi$ has no any anomalous contributions when calculating the renormalized Green's function. For the complete technical details of these calculations, including all diagrammatic contributions and their renormalization, we refer the interested reader to our paper [6].

The general structure of the Green's func-

tions Γ_i reveals that the computation of higher-order coefficients $z_{n,s}^{(i)}$ (with $s > 1$ for terms proportional to poles ε^{-s}) follows identical procedures for both static and dynamic models. The methodology developed for three-loop calculations of coefficients $z_{3,3}^{(i)}$ and $z_{3,2}^{(i)}$ (where $i = 1, 2, 3, 4$) naturally extends to higher orders. However, it is important to note that the same $\overline{\text{MS}}$ scheme must be chosen for the calculation. Additionally, in the higher order calculations, it is necessary to explicitly check whether an anomaly occurs during the calculation, in other words, all divergences containing the term $\ln(\mu^2/\tau)$ must be eliminated.

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References

- [1] U. C. Täuber. *Critical Dynamics: A Field Theory Approach to Equilibrium and Non-Equilibrium Scaling Behavior*. (Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 2014).
- [2] A. N. Vasil'ev. *The field theoretic renormalization group in critical behavior theory and stochastic dynamics*. Chapman and Hall/CRC, 2004.
- [3] H. K. Janssen, U. C. Täuber. The field theory approach to percolation processes. *Ann. Phys.* **315**, 147 (2005).
- [4] M. Borinsky, J. A. Gracey, M. V. Kompaniets, O. Schnetz, Five-loop renormalization of φ^3 theory with applications to the Lee-Yang edge singularity and percolation theory. *Phys. Rev.* **D103**, 116024 (2021).
- [5] L. T. Adzhemyan, M. Hnatič, E. V. Ivanova, M. V. Kompaniets, T. Lučivjanský, L. Mižišin. Field-theoretic analysis of directed percolation: Three-loop approximation. *Phys. Rev.* **E107**, 064138 (2023).
- [6] M. Hnatič, M. Kečer, M. V. Kompaniets, T. Lučivjanský, L. Mižišin, Y. G. Molotkov, Field-theoretic analysis of dynamic isotropic percolation: Three-loop approximation. *Phys. Rev.* **E112**, 014113 (2025).
- [7] J. L. Jacobsen, Critical points of Potts and $O(N)$ models from eigenvalue identities in periodic Temperley–Lieb algebras. *J. Phys.* **A48**, 454003 (2015).
- [8] R. J. Baxter. *Exactly solved models in statistical mechanics*. (Elsevier, 2016).
- [9] C. M. Fortuin, P. W. Kasteleyn. On the random-cluster model: I. Introduction and relation to other models. *Physica* **57**, 536 (1972).
- [10] A. Houghton, J. S. Reeve, D. J. Wallace. High-order behavior in φ^3 field theories and the percolation problem. *Phys. Rev.* **B17**, 2956 (1978).
- [11] D. K. Arrowsmith, J. W. Essam. Percolation theory on directed graphs. *J. Math. Phys.* **18**, 235 (1977).
- [12] P. C. Hohenberg, B. I. Halperin. Theory of dynamic critical phenomena. *Rev. Mod. Phys.* **49**, 435 (1977).

- [13] O. F. de Alcantara Bonfim, J. E. Kirkham, A. J. McKane. Critical exponents for the percolation problem and the Yang-Lee edge singularity. *J. Phys. A***14**, 2391 (1981).
- [14] Z. Zhang, P. Hou, S. Fang, H. Hu, Y. Deng. Critical exponents and universal excess cluster number of percolation in four and five dimensions. *Physica A***580**, 126124 (2021).